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FUR'YE QATORI YORDAMIDA BA'ZI BIR GARMONIK SONLI QATORLARNING HISOBLASH METODLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Bu maqolada garmonik sonli qatorlarni hisoblashda Fur'ye qatorlaridan qanday foydalanish mumkinligi kelib chiqadi. Unda koeffitsentlarni topish, qatorlarni soddalashtirish va ayrim garmonik qatorlarning qiymatini aniqlash bo'yicha asosiy usullar misollar bilan ko'rsatib beriladi. Ushbu metodlar hisob kitoblarni osonroq va aniqroq bajarishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Fur'ye qatori, garmonik qator, koeffitsiyentlarni hisoblash, qatorlarni soddalashtirish, yig'indilar, hisoblash metodlari.*

METHODS OF CALCULATING CERTAIN HARMONIC NUMBER SERIES USING FOURIER SERIES

ABSTRACT

This article discusses how Fourier series can be used in calculating harmonic series. It presents basic methods with examples for finding coefficients, simplifying series, and determining the values of certain harmonic series. These methods help perform calculations more easily and accurately.

Keywords: *Fourier series, harmonic series, coefficient calculation, series simplification, sums, calculation methods.*

KIRISH

Garmonik qatorlar matematik analiz va amaliy hisoblashlarda keng qo'llaniladi, ayniqsa fizik va muhandislik masalarida. Ba'zi garmonik qatorlarning yig'indilarini

aniqlash ko‘pincha murakkab hisob–kitoblarni talab qiladi. Fur‘ye qatori bu hisoblashlarni soddalashtirishda samarali vosita bo‘lib, qatorlarning koeffitsiyentlarini aniqlash va yig‘indilarini hisoblash imkonini beradi. Ushbu maqolada Fur‘ye qatori yordamida ba‘zi garmonik qatorlarni hisoblashning asosiy usullari, ularning aniqlash pirinsiplari va misollar bilan tushuntirilishi taqdim etiladi.

Trigonometrik qatorning ta’rifi. Har bir hadi

$$a_n \cos nx + b_n \sin nx \quad (n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots)$$

shaklida bo‘lgan va garmonikalardan (ohanglardan) iborat bo‘lgan quyidagi qator:

$$\frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \cos nx + b_n \sin nx) \quad (1)$$

Trigonometrik qator deb ataladi. Uning $a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3, b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, \dots$

koeffitsiyentlari *trigonometrik qatorning koeffitsiyentlari* deb yuritiladi. Odatda, trigonometrik qatorning qisman yig‘indisi quyidagicha ifodalanadi:

$$T = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \cos kx + b_n \sin kx) \quad (2)$$

va bu trigonometrik ko‘phad deb ataladi. $f(x)$ funksiyasi $[-\pi, \pi]$ oralig‘ida aniqlangan bo‘lsin. (2) qatordagi koeffitsiyentlarni kiritish uchun quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

$$a_k = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \cos(kx) dx, \quad b_k = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \sin(kx) dx$$

belgilashlarni (1) trigonometrik qatorga almashtirish natijasida (2) trigonometrik qator $f(x)$ funksiyasining Fur‘ye qatori deb ataladi.

Fur‘ye qatori formulasidan ko‘rish mumkinki, agar

$$1) \quad f(x) \text{ juft funksiya bo'lsa: } b_k = 0, \quad a_k = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \cos(kx) dx.$$

$$2) \quad f(x) \text{ toq funksiya bo'lsa: } a_k = 0, \quad b_k = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \sin(kx) dx.$$

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA

Fur‘ye qatori haqidagi batafsil ma’lumotlarni [1] adabiyotda ko‘rish mumkin. Biz ushbu maqolada Fur‘ye qatorlaridan foydalanib, ba‘zi bir sonli qatorlarning yig‘indisini topishni ko‘rib chiqamiz. Ushbu maqolada $f(x) = x^k$ ($k \in N, k \geq 5$) ko‘rinishidagi funksiyalarni $[-\pi, \pi]$ kesmada Fur‘ye qatoriga yoyamiz. Hosil bo‘lgan trigonometrik qatorlarda x ning o‘rniga ma’lum bir qiymatlarni qo‘yish orqali hosil bo‘lgan sonli qatorlarning yig‘indisini topamiz. $k \leq 4$ holatlar [2] maqolada ko‘rib chiqilgan.

NATIJALAR

Biz ushbu maqolada $k = \overline{5,6,7,8}$ holatlarni ko'rib chiqamiz:

1. $k = 5$ da. $f(x) = x^5$ ni $[-\pi; \pi]$ dagi Fur'ye qatorini topamiz.

$f(-x) = (-x)^5 = -x^5 = -f(x)$ funksiya toq funksiya. Shuning uchun

$$a_0 = 0, a_k = 0$$

$$b_k = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \sin(kx) dx = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^5 \sin(kx) dx =$$

Bu holatda bo'laklab integrallaymiz.

$$\left[u = x^5 \quad du = 5x^4 dx, \quad dv = \sin(kx) dx \quad v = -\frac{1}{k} \cos(kx) \right]$$

$$= \frac{2}{\pi} \left(-\frac{x^5}{k} \cos(kx) \right) - \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} -\frac{5}{k} x^4 \cos(kx) dx = \frac{2\pi^4}{k} (-1)^{k+1} +$$

$$\frac{10}{\pi k} \int_0^{\pi} x^4 \cos(kx) dx =$$

$$\left[\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^4 \cos(kx) dx = -\frac{8\pi^2}{k^2} (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{48}{k^4} (-1)^{k+1} \right], \quad x = \pi \text{ va } \cos \pi k =$$

$(-1)^k$ ga tengligidan foydalanamiz va b_k ni topamiz.

$$= \frac{2\pi^4}{k} (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{5}{k} \left(-8\pi^2 (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{48}{k^4} (-1)^{k+1} \right)$$

$$b_k = \frac{2\pi^4}{k} (-1)^{k+1} - \frac{40\pi^2}{k^3} (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{240}{k^5} (-1)^{k+1}$$

Fur'ye qatorini quydagicha topamiz.

$$f(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_k \sin(kx) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2\pi^4}{k} (-1)^{k+1} - \frac{40\pi^2}{k^3} (-1)^{k+1} +$$

$$\frac{240}{k^5} (-1)^{k+1} \right) \sin(kx) = \frac{\pi^5}{2} - \frac{5\pi^5}{4} + 240 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^5}$$

$$1. \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{k^3} \sin(kx) = \sin x - \frac{\sin 2x}{2} + \frac{\sin 3x}{3} - \frac{\sin 4x}{4} + \frac{\sin 5x}{5} - \dots = \left(1 - \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{11} + \dots \right) = \frac{\pi}{4}$$

$$2. \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{k^3} \sin kx = \sin x - \frac{\sin 2x}{2^3} + \frac{\sin 3x}{3^3} - \frac{\sin 4x}{4^3} + \frac{\sin 5x}{5^3} - \dots =$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_k \sin \left(\frac{\pi k}{2} \right) = b_1 - b_3 + b_5 - \dots = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} b_{2k-1} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1} (-1)^{2k}}{(2k-1)^3} =$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^3} = \frac{\pi^3}{32}$$

$$3. \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{k^5} \sin \left(\frac{\pi k}{2} \right) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} b_{2k-1} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^5}$$

Endi oxirgi ifodada $x = \frac{\pi}{2}$ deb hisoblaymiz:

$$f(x) = x^5 = \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \right)^5 = \frac{\pi^5}{2} - \frac{5\pi^5}{4} + 240 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\pi^5}{32} - \frac{\pi^5}{2} + \frac{5\pi^5}{4} &= 240 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^5} \\ 240 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^5} &= \frac{25\pi^5}{32}. \\ \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^5} &= \frac{5\pi^5}{1536}. \end{aligned}$$

2. $k = 6$ da. $f(x) = x^6$ funksiyaning $[\pi, \pi]$ dagi Fur'ye qatorini topamiz. Bu funksiya juft funksiya. $f(x) = (-x)^6 = x^6 = f(x)$ juft funksiya. Shuning uchun $b_k = 0$ Juft funksiyalar uchun Fur'ye qatori faqat kosinuslar orqali yoziladi:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= \frac{a_0}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (a_k \cos(kx)) \\ a_0 &= \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) dx = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^6 dx = \frac{2\pi^6}{7}, \\ a_k &= \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos(kx) dx = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^6 \cos(kx) dx = \\ &= \frac{2}{\pi} \left(\frac{x^6}{k} \sin kx - \int_0^{\pi} \frac{6x^5}{k} \sin kx dx \right). \end{aligned}$$

Bu integralni bo'laklab integrallaymiz. Bo'laklab integrallash formulasi:

$$\int u dv = uv - \int v du$$

Quyidagicha belgilash kiritamiz.

$$\begin{aligned} \left[u = x^6 \quad du = 6x^5 dx \quad dv = \cos kx dx \quad v = \frac{1}{k} \sin kx \right] \\ = \frac{2\pi^5 \sin \pi k}{k} - \frac{6}{k} \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^5 \sin kx dx \right) = \end{aligned}$$

$\sin \pi k = 0$ ekanligidan:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 - \frac{6}{k} \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^5 \sin kx dx \right) &= -\frac{6}{k} \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^5 \sin kx dx \right) \\ \left[\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^5 \sin kx dx \right] &= \frac{2\pi^4}{k} (-1)^{k+1} - \frac{40\pi^2}{k^3} (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{240}{k^5} (-1)^{k+1} \\ &= -\frac{6}{k} \left(\frac{2\pi^4}{k} (-1)^{k+1} - \frac{40\pi^2}{k^3} (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{240}{k^5} (-1)^{k+1} \right) \\ &= -\frac{12\pi^4}{k^2} (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{240\pi^2}{k^4} (-1)^{k+1} - \frac{1440}{k^6} (-1)^{k+1} \end{aligned}$$

Fur'ye qatorini quyidagicha topamiz:

$$f(x) = \pi^6 = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k \cos kx = \frac{\pi^6}{7} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(-\frac{12\pi^4}{k^2} (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{240\pi^2}{k^4} (-1)^{k+1} - \frac{1440}{k^6} (-1)^{k+1} \right) \cos \pi k = \frac{\pi^6}{7} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(-\frac{12\pi^4}{k^2} (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{240\pi^2}{k^4} (-1)^{k+1} - \frac{1440}{k^6} (-1)^{k+1} \right) (-1)^k = \frac{\pi^6}{7} + 12\pi^4 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^2} - 240\pi^2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^4} + 1440 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^6}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6} \quad 2 \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^4} = \frac{\pi^4}{90}$$

$$\pi^6 = \frac{\pi^6}{7} + 2\pi^6 - \frac{8\pi^6}{3} + 1440 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^6}$$

$$1440 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^6} = \pi^6 - \frac{\pi^6}{7} - 2\pi^6 + \frac{8\pi^6}{3}$$

$$1440 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^6} = \frac{32\pi^6}{21}.$$

Demak, $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^6} = \frac{\pi^6}{945}$.

3. $k = 7$ da. $f(x) = x^7$ ning $[-\pi; \pi]$ dagi Fur'ye qatorini topamiz.

$f(-x) = (-x)^7 = -x^7 = -f(x)$ toq funksiya. Shuning uchun

$a_0 = 0$, $a_k = 0$ bo'ladi. Toq funksiyalar uchun Fur'ye qatori faqat sinuslar orqali yoziladi. $f(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_k \sin kx$.

$b_k = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \sin(kx) dx = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^7 \sin kx dx$. Bu holatda bo'laklab integrallaymiz.

Quydagicha belgilash kiritamiz:

$$\left[u = x^7 \quad du = 7x^6 dx, \quad dv = \sin kx dx \quad v = -\frac{1}{k} \cos kx \right] (x = \pi)$$

$$b_k = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^7 \sin kx dx = \frac{2}{\pi} \left(\frac{-x^7}{k} \cos kx - \int_0^{\pi} \left(-\frac{1}{k} \cos kx \right) 7x^6 dx \right) =$$

$$\left(-\frac{2x^7}{\pi k} \cos kx + \frac{\left(\frac{2}{\pi}\right)^7}{k} \int_0^{\pi} x^6 \cos kx dx \right) = \left(-\frac{2\pi^6}{k} \right) (-1)^k + \frac{14}{\pi k} \int_0^{\pi} x^6 \cos kx dx =$$

$$\left(\frac{2\pi^6}{k} \right) (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{14}{\pi k} \int_0^{\pi} x^6 \cos kx dx =$$

$$1 \cdot \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^6 \cos kx dx = -\frac{12\pi^4}{k^2} (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{240\pi^2}{k^4} (-1)^{k+1} - \frac{1440}{k^6} (-1)^{k+1}$$

$$b_k = \frac{2\pi^6(-1)^{k+1}}{k} + \left(\frac{7}{k}\right) \left(-\frac{12\pi^4}{k^2} (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{240\pi^2}{k^4} (-1)^{k+1} - \frac{1440}{k^6} (-1)^{k+1} \right) =$$

$$\frac{2\pi^6(-1)^{k+1}}{k} - \frac{84\pi^4}{k^3} (-1)^{k+1} + \frac{1680\pi^2}{k^5} (-1)^{k+1} - \frac{10080}{k^7}$$

Fur'ye qatorini quydagicha topamiz

$$f(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_k \sin kx = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_k \sin\left(\frac{\pi k}{2}\right) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} b_{2k-1}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2\pi^6(-1)^{2k}}{2k-1} - \frac{84\pi^4(-1)^{2k}}{(2k-1)^3} + \frac{1680\pi^2(-1)^{2k}}{(2k-1)^5} - \frac{10080(-1)^{2k}}{(2k-1)^7} \right) (-1)^{k+1} = \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2\pi^6(-1)^{k+1}}{2k-1} - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{84\pi^4(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^3} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1680\pi^2(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^5} - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{10080(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^7} = \\ &= 2\pi^6 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{2k-1} - 84\pi^4 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^3} + 1680\pi^2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^5} - \\ &= 10080 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^7} \quad (***) \end{aligned}$$

Endi quyidagilarni e'tiborga olsamiz:

1. $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{2k-1} = \frac{\pi}{4}.$
2. $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^3} = \frac{\pi^3}{32}.$
3. $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^5} = \frac{5\pi^5}{1536}.$

U holda (***) quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= 2\pi^6 \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) - 84\pi^4 \left(\frac{\pi^3}{32}\right) + 1680\pi^2 \left(\frac{5\pi^5}{1536}\right) - 10080 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^7} = \frac{\pi^7}{2} - \\ &= \frac{21\pi^7}{8} + \frac{175\pi^7}{32} - 10080 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^7} = \frac{107\pi^7}{32} - 10080 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^7} \end{aligned}$$

Endi $x = \frac{\pi}{2}$ deb olsak:

$$\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^7 = \frac{107\pi^7}{32} - 10080 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^7}$$

$$\frac{\pi^7}{128} = \frac{107\pi^7}{32} - 10080 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^7}$$

$$10080 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^7} = \frac{427\pi^7}{128}.$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{(2k-1)^7} = \frac{61\pi^7}{184320}.$$

4. $k = 8$ da. $f(x) = x^8$ ni $[-\pi; \pi]$ dagi Fur'ye qatorini topamiz.

$f(-x) = (-x)^8 = f(x)$ juft funksiya. Shuning uchun

$b_k = 0$. Juft funksiyalar uchun Fur'ye qatori faqat kosinuslar orqali yoziladi:

$$f(x) = \frac{a_0}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (a_k \cos(kx))$$

$$a_0 = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) dx = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} x^8 dx = \frac{2\pi^9}{9\pi} = \frac{2\pi^8}{9}.$$

Demak $\frac{a_0}{2} = \frac{\pi^8}{9}$.

$$a_k = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x) \cos(kx) dx = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi x^8 \cos kx dx.$$

Bu integralni bo‘laklab integrallaymiz. Bo‘laklab integrallash formulasi: Quydagicha belgilash kiritamiz

$$\left[u = x^8 \quad du = 8x^7 dx, \quad dv = \cos kx dx \quad v = \frac{1}{k} \sin kx \right]$$

$$= \frac{2}{\pi} \left(\frac{x^8}{k} \sin kx - \frac{8}{k} \int_0^\pi x^7 \sin kx dx \right) =$$

Bu holatda $x = \pi$ va $\sin \pi k = 0$:

$$a_k = \frac{2}{\pi} \left(\frac{\pi^8}{k} \cdot 0 \right) - \frac{8}{k} \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi x^7 \sin kx dx \right) = -\frac{8}{k} \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi x^7 \sin kx dx \right)$$

$$\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi x^7 \sin kx dx = \frac{2\pi^6(-1)^{k+1}}{k} - \frac{84\pi^4}{k^3}(-1)^{k+1} + \frac{1680\pi^2}{k^5}(-1)^{k+1} - \frac{10080}{k^7}$$

$$a_k = -\frac{8}{k} \left(\frac{2\pi^6(-1)^{k+1}}{k} - \frac{84\pi^4}{k^3}(-1)^{k+1} + \frac{1680\pi^2}{k^5}(-1)^{k+1} - \frac{10080}{k^7} \right) =$$

$$\frac{-16\pi^6(-1)^{k+1}}{k^2} + \frac{672\pi^4}{k^4}(-1)^{k+1} - \frac{13440\pi^2}{k^6}(-1)^{k+1} + \frac{80640}{k^8}$$

Fur'ye qatorini quydagicha topamiz $x = \pi$ va $\cos \pi k = (-1)^k$

$$f(x) = x^8 = \pi^8 = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^\infty a_k \cos kx = \frac{\pi^8}{9} + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \left(\frac{-16\pi^6(-1)^{k+1}}{k^2} + \frac{672\pi^4}{k^4}(-1)^{k+1} - \frac{13440\pi^2}{k^6}(-1)^{k+1} + \frac{80640}{k^8} \right) \cos kx = \frac{\pi^8}{9} + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \left(\frac{-16\pi^6(-1)^{k+1}}{k^2} + \frac{672\pi^4}{k^4}(-1)^{k+1} - \frac{13440\pi^2}{k^6}(-1)^{k+1} + \frac{80640}{k^8} \right) (-1)^k = \frac{\pi^8}{9} + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \left(\frac{16\pi^6(-1)^{2k}}{k^2} - \frac{672\pi^4}{k^4}(-1)^{2k} + \frac{13440\pi^2}{k^6}(-1)^{2k} - \frac{80640}{k^8} \right) = \frac{\pi^8}{9} + 16\pi^6 \sum_{k=1}^\infty \frac{1}{k^2} - 672\pi^4 \sum_{k=1}^\infty \frac{1}{k^4} + 13440\pi^2 \sum_{k=1}^\infty \frac{1}{k^6} - 80640 \sum_{k=1}^\infty \frac{1}{k^8}$$

$$1. \sum_{k=1}^\infty \frac{1}{k^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$$

$$2. \sum_{k=1}^\infty \frac{1}{k^4} = \frac{\pi^4}{90}$$

$$3. \sum_{k=1}^\infty \frac{1}{k^6} = \frac{\pi^6}{945} \text{ tengligidan foydalanib Fur'ye qatorini topamiz:}$$

$$\pi^8 = \frac{\pi^8}{9} + 16\pi^6 \left(\frac{\pi^2}{6} \right) - 672\pi^4 \left(\frac{\pi^4}{90} \right) + 13440\pi^2 \left(\frac{\pi^6}{945} \right) - 80640 \sum_{k=1}^\infty \frac{1}{k^8}$$

$$\frac{\pi^8}{9} + \frac{16\pi^8}{6} - \frac{672\pi^8}{90} + \frac{13440\pi^8}{945} - \pi^8 = 80640 \sum_{k=1}^\infty \frac{1}{k^8}$$

$$80640 \sum_{k=1}^\infty \frac{1}{k^8} = \frac{768\pi^8}{90}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^8} = \frac{\pi^8}{9450}.$$

MUHOKAMA

Yuqoridagi hisob-kitoblarda ko‘rish mumkinki, juft funksiyalar uchun $x = \pi$ holatni, toq funksiyalar uchun $x = \pi/2$ holatni tanlab oldik. Bu holatlar mos ravishda juft va toq funksiyali vaziyatlarda qulay hisob-kitoblarga olib keladi. Takidlash joizki, x o‘zgaruvchiga $[-\pi, \pi]$ to‘plamdan turli xil qiymatlar berib, Fur‘ye qatori yordamida ko‘plab sonli qatorlarning yig‘indisini hisoblash mumkin.

XULOSA

Ushbu maqolada Fur‘ye qatorlari yordamida ba’zi bir sonli qatorlarning yig‘indisini topish metodi ko‘rsatildi. Na’mana sifatida $k = 5, 6, 7, 8$ bo‘lgan holatlarda misollar ko‘rsatildi. Aytish joizki, yuqoridagi metodlarni qo‘llagan holda, $k > 8$ dagi holatlarni ham hisoblash chiqish mumkin. Undan tashqari x ga $\pi/2$ va π dan boshqa qiymatlarni qo‘yish orqali yana boshqa turli xil sonli qatorlarning yig‘indisini topish ham mumkin. Kelgusidagi tadqiqotlarda $f(x) = x^k$ ko‘rinishdagi funksiyalardan boshqa ko‘rinishdagi funksiyalarni ham Fur‘ye qatoriga yoyish orqali yana turli xil sonli qatorlarning yig‘indisini hisoblash mumkin. Undan tashqari funksiyalarni ixtiyoriy $[-l, l]$ kesmada Fur‘ye qatorlariga yoyish orqali yana ham ko‘p natijalarga erishish mumkin.

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